

AQUARIUS

TA Data Management Follow-up I

MARIS

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Acronyms and abbreviations

ADD	AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard
CSR	Cruise Summary Report
EDMO	European Directory of Marine Organisations
NODC	National Oceanographic Data Centre
TA	Transnational Access
UUID	Universally Unique IDentifier

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1. Introduction

AQUARIUS Transnational Access (TA) Funding Calls are launched inviting European and international researchers to submit proposals. So far two Calls have taken place, one at Month 9 and one at Month 19, which targeted themes for each of the four Mission Ocean lighthouse regions, consisting of the Atlantic & Arctic Basin, Mediterranean Sea, Baltic and North Sea Basins, and Black Sea, along with their associated rivers. Each of these Calls were open for a period of two months and followed by a scientific and logistical evaluation, taking altogether circa seven months for taking decisions on the TA proposals that are awarded and planned. From the first Call 3 TA events have already taken place in 2025 and currently another 5 TA events are planned for 2026.

AQUARIUS has adopted an **open data policy**, which is implemented with a **dedicated Data Management approach**, to ensure that all gathered and generated metadata and data will be managed in line with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and become part of the archives managed and operated by leading European data management infrastructures for quality assurance, long term stewardship, and wide access and use, as well as for sharing with EMODnet, Copernicus Marine, EDITO, and global repositories.

The AQUARIUS Data Management approach covers multiple steps in the deployment of TA events, going from planning to reporting a summary of observations to gathering and standardising all collected data sets. This way, over time all information, metadata and data sets from the TA events are to be published as open data and made widely accessible. This is achieved by a close cooperation between the TA scientific teams and the expert data centres that are active in WP6 for supporting data management and in WP5 for giving training about data management and prevailing European standards.

This **Deliverable D6.4** documents the progress with implementing the AQUARIUS Data Management approach for the first 3 TA events that had their field work in 2025 and it gives an outlook on the planning for the next 5 TA events in 2026.

2. AQUARIUS Data Management approach

As part of the AQUARIUS TA events, many new data sets in a large variety of data types will be collected by the TA scientific teams, making use and combining multiple and different observation installations as provided. AQUARIUS has adopted an **open data policy**, which is being implemented with a **dedicated data management approach**, to ensure that all gathered and generated metadata and data will be managed in line with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

In order to ensure quality assurance, long-term stewardship and wide access and use of the data collected in the AQUARIUS TA events, it is envisaged that the data and metadata, and possible resulting data products, become part of the repositories managed and operated by the leading European data management infrastructures, namely SeaDataNet¹ (physics, bathymetry, chemistry, biology, geology), EurOBIS² (biodiversity), ELIXIR-ENA³ (biogenomics), ICOS-Ocean⁴ (carbon), and Copernicus INSTAC⁵ (Near- Real-Time data). Achieving this, will also ensure that the AQUARIUS data and data products will become available through EMODnet, Copernicus Marine, Blue-Cloud (EOSC), the European Digital Twin Ocean (DTO) developments, and globally to e.g. GEOSS, and the digital ocean ecosystem that is being developed in the framework of the UN-IOC Ocean Decade programme.

The Data Management approach can be summarised as follows:

- **Aim: make data and data products resulting from TA activities openly available in line with FAIR principles** through established European data management infrastructures and within the lifetime of the AQUARIUS project. The primary responsibility for achieving this lies with the TA scientific teams.
- **Effectiveness:** To get a maximum result and impact, the **TA scientific teams will be supported and work together with expert data centres**, which are well acquainted with the principles, standards, and related tools and services for implementing the AQUARIUS data management approach.
- **Expertise: Most expert data centres are National Oceanographic Data Centres (NODCs)**, geographically spread over Europe in the four EU Mission Lighthouse regions, and together sharing expertise for handling different data types and disciplines of relevance for AQUARIUS.
- **Synergy, Guidance, Support:** These **expert data centres will work together with the TA scientific teams from the moment that the TA proposals have been awarded** in order to make the TA scientific teams more aware and educated in the AQUARIUS data management approach and to support them in the actual deployment before, during, and after the TA activities.

¹<https://www.seadatanet.org>

²<https://www.eurobis.org>

³<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/>

⁴<https://www.icos-cp.eu/observations/ocean/otc>

⁵<https://marine.copernicus.eu/about/producers/insitu-tac>

Figure 2.1: Overview of the AQUARIUS Data Management approach

2.1. Data Management Flow scheme

The AQUARIUS Data Management approach is described in detail in **Deliverable D6.2 – AQUARIUS Data Management Plan**⁶. The following table is extracted from D6.2 and gives the AQUARIUS data management flow scheme, which includes a number of steps from planning to training to deployment to publishing, and a number of instruments, which should be applied in those steps.

Steps	Activities	Support
Step 1a – pre-planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AQUARIUS Data Management Plan D6.2 included in guidelines for TA proposers 	Expert data centres can provide advice upon request
Step 1b – pre-planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TA project proposers complete initial Data Management Plan for their project, following AQUARIUS DMP template phase 1, and include this in their TA project proposal 	Expert data centres review DMP phase 1 in support of Call evaluation process
Step 2a – planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> After awarding of TA project, TA proposers are asked to refine their initial Data Management Plan for their project, following AQUARIUS DMP template phase 2 Validated TA DMP phase 2 will be published on AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard (ADD) 	Expert data centres give support and advice to TA project scientific team MARIS
Step 2b – planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Preparation of promotional factsheet of the TA project and publishing on AQUARIUS website 	WP7 team together with TA project scientific team

⁶<https://zenodo.org/records/13642869>

Steps	Activities	Support
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to promotional factsheet of TA project included in AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard (ADD) 	MARIS
Step 3 – training in data management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training in data management organised by webinars for TA project scientific teams • Recorded webinars and presentations made available on AQUARIUS website 	Expert data centres, led by HCMR WP7 team
Step 4 - deployment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data gathering and processing undertaken by TA project scientific teams, supported by providers of AQUARIUS research infrastructure services • During TA activities, PI of TA project scientific team is requested to maintain an AQUARIUS TA Data Summary Log with an index of data gathering activities • In case the TA project will involve scientific cruises with Research Vessels, then also a Cruise Summary Report (CSR)⁷ should be completed by the TA project PI within a month after the cruise. • Completed TA Data Summary Log for selected TA project will be published on AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard (ADD) • If applicable, a link to the Cruise Summary Report on the SeaDataNet portal will be published on the AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard (ADD) 	Expert data centres are available for advice and support for data management issues MARIS provides a Tablet with App for maintaining TA Data Summary Log TA project scientific team (PI) MARIS MARIS
Step 5 – data processing and transfer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TA project scientific teams undertake efforts for transforming metadata and data to standard formats as valid for applicable European data management infrastructure(s) • Transfer of elaborated metadata and data as packages, sorted for data types / disciplines, through the Data Submission service of EMODnet Ingestion⁸ or 	Coaching and support by expert data centres Reception of data and metadata packages and assignment to selected expert data centres

⁷<https://www.seadatanet.org/Metadata/CSR-Cruises>

⁸<https://www.emodnet-ingestion.eu>

Steps	Activities	Support
	<p>SeaDataNet SeaNoe service⁹, to expert data centres</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Links to submissions in EMODnet Ingestion and SeaNoe will be published on AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard (ADD) 	MARIS
Step 6 – publishing of data and metadata in FAIR way	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Received data and metadata will be reviewed by assigned expert data centres with feedback to TA project scientific teams. • Validated data and metadata will be included in local data centres and populated into the applicable European data management infrastructure(s) • Links to inclusions in European data management infrastructure(s) will be published on AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard (ADD) 	Expert data centres in contact with TA PIs Expert data centres MARIS
Step 7 – training in open science practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training in open science and use of the Blue-Cloud VRE and its applications, organised by webinars for TA project scientific teams • Recorded webinars and presentations made available in the training hub on the AQUARIUS website 	Blue-Cloud VRE experts, led by CNR WP7 team
Step 8 – practising open science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TA researchers encouraged to register in Blue-Cloud VRE • TA researchers performing analytics on their newly acquired data sets, possibly in combination with data from established data repositories, using Blue-Cloud applications 	CNR Coaching and support by Blue-Cloud VRE experts
Step 9a – publishing of data products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TA researchers documenting open science data products with metadata in the Blue-Cloud VRE data products catalogue which are shared with EOSC and Zenodo • Links to published data products will be published on AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard (ADD) 	Coaching and support by Blue-Cloud VRE experts MARIS

⁹<https://www.seadatanet.org/Software/SEANOE>

Steps	Activities	Support
Step 9b – publishing of scientific publications (papers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TA researchers preparing potential scientific publications (papers) about their TA projects which could be published with DOIs in Zenodo • Links to scientific publications will be published on AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard (ADD) and promoted via AQUARIUS channels 	TA researchers MARIS and WP7
Step 10 – FAIR indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expert data centres maintaining and publishing best practices and FAIRness indicators for the AQUARIUS data flow and its achievements; inclusion by VRE experts about uptake and results of open science practices 	Expert data centres and VRE experts

Table 2.1: Overview of the AQUARIUS Data Management Flow scheme

Note: the TA projects might deal with different types of data that could require splitting of packages over multiple expert data centres. In addition, some data types will be available directly during the TA activities (Real time mode), while others are samples that need to be processed in laboratories and/or with dedicated software, which will take extra time and could also imply waiting times (Delayed mode).

2.2. TA Summary Log APP

As part of the data management (DM) flow, TA teams will have to maintain a summary of the observations that they collect on a daily basis. This gives a **TA Summary Log** which is published after the TA events on the AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard (ADD). It provides the AQUARIUS Data Management experts with a metadata overview of all data sets and samples that have been collected during each TA event. The DM experts will use this overview information to plan ahead, to know what data is coming, who to contact, and how to divide among expert data centres. They will also maintain a follow-up scheme so that there is a clear overview of assignments, data flow status, and achieved throughput.

For the purpose of completing the TA Summary Log, MARIS in consultation with the WP6 team has developed a dedicated APP, with graphics designed by Seascope Belgium (SSBE) to be in line with AQUARIUS branding, that should be used by each TA team during the TA events. An initial Beta version of the APP was tested by colleagues from Ifremer and RBINS in March 2025. After processing of identified issues, a second Beta version was tested by Ifremer and RBINS in April 2025 with a successful outcome. The APP was released in May 2025 in anticipation of the first TA events. It was also presented during the 1st AQUARIUS Data Management Training Workshop in June 2025, organised by WP5 for the scientific teams of the first group of TA events. In practice of a TA event, it will be the responsibility of the Principal Investigator (PI) or Chief Investigator (CI) to gather the required information from the team members and to populate the APP on a daily basis.

Home

Navigation Menu

Organisations

Equipment

Figure 2.2: Screenshots of the TA Summary Log APP

The APP facilitates configuring a Project Description for the TA event and sub-setting the lists of controlled vocabularies for the vocabulary terms, which will be relevant in connection with the specific TA event. This will make the use of the vocabularies, when entering observation metadata during the TA event, more efficient.

The APP can function on a stand-alone basis and without internet connection on an Android tablet. However, the internet should be used for updating (refreshing) the controlled vocabularies once in a while, and for submitting the TA Summary Log from the APP to the AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard (ADD). This should be done at least every 2 weeks after the TA event, but can also be done during the TA event as each time the previous TA Log will be overwritten with the latest after successful import. The ADD features a datahub API to receive the metadata files in APP JSON format and to import these into the TA Summary Log database. Each TA event will have its own Universally Unique Identifier (UUID).

2.3. AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard (ADD)

The results of each of the data management flow steps are published on the **AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard (ADD)**, which is a dedicated section on the AQUARIUS website. For several steps this includes publishing dedicated links to European services which are adopted for populating and publishing the AQUARIUS TA events and their output.

The outline of the AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard (ADD) has been developed by MARIS in consultation with the WP6 team, and developed as a dedicated platform integrated in the AQUARIUS website by Seascope Belgium. It allows users to follow

progress of the data management flow scheme for each TA event from planning stage through to publishing of results for each awarded TA project. The ADD can be found at: <https://add.aquarius-ri.eu>, or under the 'Data' menu on the AQUARIUS website. It was launched in July 2025 with an online Content Management System (CMS) and a front end, including an API for receiving TA Summary Log submissions from the APP.

Figure 2.3: Homepage of the AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard

TA Event	Research Infrastructure	Date start	Date end	Details
DENGATE	RV G. O. Sars , AUV Barabas , Glider Yoko	2027-01-01	2028-02-28	View project
ABACUS 2026 Mission 2	SOCIB Glider Facility	2026-09-08	2026-10-03	View project
ABACUS 2026 Mission 1	SOCIB Glider Facility	2026-05-15	2026-06-09	View project
BASEVOC	Uto Marine and Atmospheric Research Station	2025-04-01	2025-09-28	View project
ASTRA	RV Tubitak Marmara	2025-09-05	2025-09-20	View project
STREAM-DANUBE	RV Mare Nigrum	2025-09-01	2025-09-13	View project

Figure 2.4: Overview of TA events at the AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard

For each TA event, there is up-to-date and public information about each TA project and their progress. The ultimate goal is to give discovery and public access to research data sets as collected and processed and data products as generated by the TA research teams as part of the AQUARIUS TA projects.

ASTRA

Project Info	
TA Project ID	ASTRA
TA Project Information	
Start Date	2025-09-05
End Date	2025-09-20
Data Management Plan	Download file
Summary Data Log	Summary Data Log
Cruise Summary Report (RVs)	-
Original Research Data in EMODnet Ingestion	-
Original Research Data in SeaDataNet SEANOE	-
Elaborate Research Data in European repositories	-
Elaborate Open Science Data Products	-
Research Infrastructure	RV Tubitak Marmara

Figure 2.5: Information page for each TA event

Figure 2.6: TA Summary Log of selected TA event

2.4. AQUARIUS Data Management Experts

The AQUARIUS WP6 team contains several expert data centres that can be assigned to provide coaching and support to TA scientific teams for deploying the data management approach. The assignment will take into account the lighthouse regions and the specific data type expertise of the expert data centres. The following table gives an overview of the available expert data centres.

Table 2.2: Overview of the AQUARIUS Data Centre experts

Organisation	Data management infrastructure(s) related to	Lighthouse region(s)
OGS - Italy	NODC, SeaDataNet, EuroBIS, Copernicus INSTAC, EMODnet, Blue-Cloud	Mediterranean

HCMR - Greece	NODC, SeaDataNet, EurOBIS, Copernicus INSTAC, EMODnet, Blue-Cloud	Mediterranean, Danube - Black Sea
SMHI - Sweden	NODC, SeaDataNet, Copernicus INSTAC, EMODnet, Blue-Cloud	Baltic-North Sea, Atlantic-Arctic
NIMRD - Romania	NODC, SeaDataNet, EMODnet	Danube - Black Sea
CSIC - Spain	NODC, SeaDataNet, EurOBIS, EMODnet	Mediterranean, Atlantic-Arctic
IFREMER - France	NODC, SeaDataNet (operator), Copernicus INSTAC (operator), EurOBIS, EMODnet. Blue-Cloud	Mediterranean, Atlantic-Arctic
MI - Ireland	NODC, SeaDataNet, EurOBIS, Copernicus INSTAC, EMODnet	Baltic-North Sea, Atlantic-Arctic
RBINS - Belgium	NODC, SeaDataNet, EMODnet	Baltic-North Sea
IMR - Norway	NODC, SeaDataNet, EurOBIS, Copernicus INSTAC, EMODnet	Atlantic-Arctic
VLIZ - Belgium	NODC, SeaDataNet, EurOBIS (operator), EMODnet. Blue-Cloud	Baltic-North Sea
EMBRC-ERIC - France	EurOBIS, SeaDataNet, EMOBON, Blue-Cloud	Mediterranean, Atlantic-Arctic, Danube - Black Sea, Baltic-North Sea
NORCE - Norway	ICOS-Marine (operator)	Mediterranean, Atlantic-Arctic, Danube - Black Sea, Baltic-North Sea
EMSO-ERIC - Italy	EMSO-ERIC, Blue-Cloud	Mediterranean, Atlantic-Arctic, Danube - Black Sea

3. Progress with Data Management approach for TA events

Following the Calls, TA events were and will be selected and planned for deployment. For each TA event expert data centres were and will be assigned to provide coaching and support to the TA scientific teams to ensure that all steps of the AQUARIUS Data Management Flow scheme are undertaken. The results of the data management flow steps are published on the **AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard (ADD)** so that they can be followed over time.

3.1. Current overview of events and assigned data centres

At the time of writing of this Deliverable, multiple TA events have been selected as an outcome of the 1st Call. The deployment of their field work, using the AQUARIUS research infrastructures, is planned during the years 2025 – 2027. The following table gives a concise overview of the selected and agreed TA events and the assigned data centres.

Table 3.1: Overview of selected TA events and assignment of AQUARIUS expert data centres (status 6 February 2026)

TA event	Assigned Expert Data Centre(s)			Year	Lighthouse Region	P.I. organisation	Country
ASTRA	NIMRD	HCMR	EMBL-EBI	2025	Danube & Black Sea	National Institute for Marine Research and Development “Grigore Antipa” (NIMRD)	Romania
BASEVOC	SMHI	RBINS		2025	Baltic & North Sea	University of Copenhagen	Denmark
STREAM-DANUBE	NIMRD	HCMR		2025	Danube & Black Sea	Helmholtz Center Hereon	Germany
ABACUS 2026	OGS	CSIC		2026	Mediterranean Sea	University of Naples Parthenope	Italy
GREAT	MI	EMBL-EBI	(IMR)	2026	Atlantic-Arctic	Greenland Institute of Natural Resources	Denmark
EddiesGC	(VLIZ)	(IFREMER)		2026	Atlantic-Arctic	Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ)	Belgium
ARE7E-2026	MI	(RBINS)		2026	Atlantic-Arctic	National Oceanography Centre (NOC)	United Kingdom
DEEP-IMPACT	HCMR	OGS	EMBL-EBI	2026	Mediterranean Sea	National Institute of Oceanography and Experimental Geophysics (OGS)	Italy
CRUST	EMBL-EBI	?		2027	Atlantic-Arctic	Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland	Denmark
DENGATE	?	?		2027	Atlantic-Arctic	University of Birmingham	United Kingdom

It should be noted that the assignments of data centres for TA projects that will be deployed in 2026 and 2027 are still under discussion among the expert data centres and will soon be fixed, in particular for those being deployed in 2026. In addition, more TA events are to be expected from the 2nd Call and these might be planned for deployment, starting in 2027 and further.

3.2. Current status for TA events in 2025

Three TA projects of the first TA Call (i.e. ASTRA, STREAM-DANUBE, and BASEVOC) deployed and executed their project in 2025 (see Table 3.1). Two (ASTRA and STREAM-DANUBE) have been assigned to NIMRD and HCMR as the TA events take

place in the Danube and Black Sea region. For ASTRA also EMBL-EBI might be involved as it also concerns bio-genomic data sets. The 3rd TA event, BASEVOC, has been assigned to SMHI and RBINS as it concerns the Baltic & North Sea region. In all cases, the Principal Investigators (PIs) have been contacted to discuss the data management support and they also have been invited, possibly with other team members, to participate in the Training Workshop, organised by WP5 in June 2025.

The assigned data centres have reviewed the respective initial Data Management Plans (DMPs) which were prepared by the PIs as part of their proposal application. PIs have adjusted their DMPs according to the reviews and the final DMPs have been published on the AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard. The reviews focused in particular on assuring that the collected data together with FAIR metadata would be made ready for depositing in the European repositories which are selected for AQUARIUS. In the meantime, partner SSBE produced factsheets for each of the TA projects providing an illustrated narrative on the objectives, partners, and implementation of each of the TA events. These factsheets are published in the AQUARIUS website and also linked in the AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard.

Following the guidance and steps, the PIs have been contacted for downloading and installing the AQUARIUS TA Summary Log APP. This was successfully achieved and all three TA teams made use of a Tablet of their own. As a first step, the PIs have configured their TA events, narrowing down involved organisations, equipment, research infrastructures, and data types. During this process there was interaction with MARIS for updating some of the vocabularies for missing terms. Also, a few minor bugs were reported, which were immediately fixed, so that the PIs could use the APP during their field work without issues.

Once finalised, the PIs uploaded their TA Summary Logs from the APP to the API on the AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard for publication. As next step, the assigned data centres contacted the PIs concerning the preparation of the observation metadata and data for ingestion and elaboration. All three TA events collected not only direct observations, but also a lot of samples, which require time for laboratory analyses and further processing. As a consequence, it is expected that the actual data and metadata ingestion and elaboration will take place in the second half of 2026. The assigned data centres will check regularly. Moreover, the PIs and members of their teams will be invited to the next WP5 training workshop that is planned in the first quarters of 2026. This will facilitate refreshing the understanding and approaches for preparing the metadata and data in a FAIR way.

3.3. Planning for TA events in 2026

The information about the TA events that will deploy in 2026 became recently available in January 2026. Of the seven TA events, five are planning their field work around and after the summer of 2026. The PIs will be invited to the 2nd WP5 Training Workshop that will be organised in the first quarter of 2026. Moreover, SSBE already has made factsheets for these new TA events, which are published on the AQUARIUS website and linked in the AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard. WP6 is in the progress of assigning expert data centres to each new TA project, whereby a few have already been agreed. The next step will be that the assigned data centres make a review of the initial Data Management Plans and contact the PIs to discuss their DMP observations and work on finalising the DMPs for publishing on the AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard.

The following table provides the current situation with regards to completing the Data Management steps for all TA events that have been selected, agreed, deployed, and planned for 2025 – 2027 as a result of the 1st Call. The review and decision procedure

for the 2nd Call results is underway and will lead to more TA events, most probably starting in 2027.

In addition to the external AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard, an internal WP6 online schema has been set up, which will require the assigned data centres to report regularly on their progress with the TA events. This will include more details about data collections and data types, to be distributed among assigned data centres, taking into account their specific expertise and access to repositories.

Table 3.1: Current status of completion of Data Management steps for selected TA events (status 6 February 2026)

TA event	Project ID	TA Project Info	Start Date	End Date	Summary Data Log	CSR	Data in EMODnet Ingestion	Data in SeaDataNet SEANOE	Elaborated data in European repositories	Elaborated open science data products	Research Infrastructure
ASTRA	*	*	*	*	*						*
BASEVOC	*	*	*	*	*						*
STREAM-DANUBE	*	*	*	*	*						*
ABACUS 2026	*	*	*	*							*
GREAT	*	*									*
EddiesGC	*	*									*
ARE7E-2026	*	*									*
DEEP-IMPACT	*	*	*	*							*
CRUST	*	*									*
DENGATE	*	*	*	*							*

4. Conclusions

This **Deliverable D6.4** documents that good progress is being made with the implementation of the AQUARIUS Data Management approach for the TA events that have been selected and agreed so far. The additional tools and services, namely the AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard and the TA Summary Log APP, have been taken into production and are performing well to expectations. There is a close cooperation with WP5 concerning Training Workshops to introduce TA scientific teams to the Data Management approach, the target European repositories, the metadata and data standards, and the tools and services for achieving the goals. WP6 brings together an active group of expert data centres that are dividing their efforts for coaching and giving DM support to the TA scientific teams, taking into account the lighthouse regions of TA events, and the types of data that are to be collected in the TA events. So far, only a few TA events are under their guidance, but this will increase gradually, following the outcomes of the AQUARIUS Calls. The organisation and technical means are 'ready to roll' for this increase.